

STRATEGIES USED BY COLLEGE TEACHERS TO MOTIVATE STUDENTS IN ONLINE TEACHING-LEARNING AS RELATED TO THEIR COMPUTER EFFICACY

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Abstract

The present study explored the differences in strategies used by college teachers to motivate their students in online teaching and learning in relation to their computer efficacy. The descriptive survey research design was employed in the study to collect the data from 270 college teachers. The researchers employed self-developed research tools in the study. An item-wise analysis through t-test as a statistical technique was used to examine the significance of the difference regarding the use of strategies by college teachers having high and low computer-eficacy to motivate students in online teaching-learning environments. The findings of the study revealed that significant differences between college teachers having high and low computer efficacy were found in the use of text messages and audio messages for sending introductory notes to students regarding the topic to be taught in online classes. The significant differences were also found in the use of WhatsApp groups and Twitter chats for encouraging students to engage with each other and with the course material. There were also significant differences in the usage of interactive videos, animations and simulations for facilitating students' interests in the subject matter among college teachers having high and low computer efficacy. Overall, the findings highlighted that professional development programmes need to be addressed to train college teachers to use various strategies while teaching in an online environment based on their levels of computer efficacy.

Keywords: *Computer efficacy, online teaching-learning, student motivation, motivational strategies, higher education, digital competencies, technology integration*

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the widespread use of online teaching and learning methodologies, which have drastically changed the higher education landscape (Darius et al., 2021). Educational institutions around the world had to move from traditional face-to-face teaching to online classrooms, bringing novel challenges for teachers (Singh & Hurley, 2017). For college teachers, maintaining students' motivation has become crucial in this new educational setting. An essential component of academic achievement is student motivation, defined as the psychological drive that promotes learning and shapes the effort and direction of students' work (Yang, 2023). Maintaining student interest is particularly challenging in online environments because instant non-verbal cues and physical presence are absent (Valentin et al., 2013). Teachers need to use various technological strategies to draw students' attention, maintain their interest, and promote ongoing participation in the course content. According to Bandura's (1977) social cognitive theory, Computer efficacy is a person's belief in their ability to use a computer effectively for specific tasks. In online teaching, computer efficacy refers to teachers' confidence in using learning management systems, developing multimedia content, and facilitating technology-based interactions (Sehar & Alwi, 2023). Research consistently indicates that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs have a significant impact on their teaching practices and their willingness to adopt technology (Akram et al., 2022). Teachers who have high computer efficacy are more likely to try new digital tools, overcome technical challenges, and develop engaging online experiences (Surry & Land, 2000). The teachers who have low computer efficacy may experience anxiety, avoid technology-heavy strategies, and adhere to traditional methods, which might be less effective in virtual settings, ultimately hindering their students' learning experiences and engagement in the digital environment.

Keller's ARCS Model of Motivation (1983) emphasises four key elements, viz., Attention, Relevance, Confidence and Satisfaction. All four of these elements serve as the theoretical foundation for the understanding of student motivation in online learning. To be truly impactful, online teaching must take into account all these factors. This implies that to keep students' attention a number of steps must be taken which include: Provision of different kinds of interesting content; Ensuring the relevance of material by linking the material directly to the personal aspirations and interests of the students; Giving the students various challenges and regular feedback to boost their confidence; and Providing them with rewards, both intrinsic and extrinsic, for successful learning experience, in order to promote satisfaction. In digital

settings, activating these motivating components depends on technology, making teachers' computer self-efficacy potentially a crucial factor in their ability to execute effective motivational strategies.

Rationale and Significance of the Study

There exists extensive study on the integration of technology in higher education (Aithal & Kumar, 2016; Mishra et al., 2023) and on student motivation (Yang, 2023). However, not much research has looked at how teachers' computer skills affect the motivational strategies they choose and use in online teaching and learning. Understanding this link is important for a number of reasons. For example, it can help create professional development programs that meet the needs of teachers with different levels of computer skills. Second, it can help institutions make decisions about how to support technology and build infrastructure. Third, it can help with the bigger goal of improving the quality of online education by finding out what motivated, tech-savvy teachers do that works.

Research Objective

The primary objective of the study was to examine item-wise significant differences in the strategies used by college teachers having high and low computer efficacy to motivate students in online teaching-learning.

2. Review of Literature

Bandura's (1977) self-efficacy theory is a primary framework for understanding computer efficacy. This theory suggests that self-efficacy beliefs are formed from four main sources: mastery experiences (successfully completing tasks), vicarious experiences (observing others succeed), verbal persuasion (encouragement by others) and physiological/emotional states (anxious or positive feelings). In the context of technology use, teachers who have effectively integrated technology into their teaching (mastery experiences) are more likely to develop stronger beliefs in their computer efficacy. Sehar and Alwi (2023) extended this framework to online teaching, showing that teachers' digital skills are significantly related to their self-efficacy in managing online classes, especially regarding instructional strategies and student engagement. Their research indicated a correlation of 0.839 between digital competency and self-efficacy, with $p < 0.001$, signifying a strong positive relationship.

Aithal (2023) put forward a detailed plan for how to use Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) to change higher education in India. Researchers pointed out how artificial intelligence, robotics, big data, blockchain, cloud computing, and virtual reality could all make education more accessible and better. The National Education Policy 2020 in

India clearly states that technology is an important tool for making higher education better and more accessible (Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2020). To encourage learning through technology, some digital initiatives have been started, such as SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) (Mishra et al., 2023). However, the successful implementation of these initiatives ultimately depends on teachers' ability and willingness to utilize technology effectively in their instructional practices. Darius et al. (2021), in their survey of 450 university and college students in South India, identified several methods that promote effective online learning: animations, digital collaborations with peers, video lectures delivered by faculty handling the subject, online quizzes with multiple-choice questions, student version software, conducive home environments, faculty interactions during lectures, and online materials provided by faculty. These results highlight the significance of diverse technology strategies in sustaining student engagement.

Yang (2023) explored strategies for motivating students in college English instruction, highlighting the significance of fostering positive teacher-student relationships, employing varied pedagogical approaches, cultivating stimulating classroom atmospheres, delivering constructive learning feedback, and integrating multimedia technologies and resources. These strategies are mostly for traditional classrooms, but they can also be utilised online. Surry and Land (2000) suggested a framework to get college teachers to adopt technology based on Keller's ARCS Model. Researchers argued that administrators must understand technological change from the faculty's perspective and develop strategies that address attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction. Their research underscores the significance of individual faculty attributes, such as technological proficiency, as factors influencing adoption trends. In a systematic review, Akram et al. (2022) investigated teachers' perceptions of technology integration in Pakistan and found that teachers generally have positive views on technology integration. However, they encounter obstacles such as slow internet speeds, power outages, insufficient infrastructure, limited online teaching experience, and inadequate training. The study emphasizes that teachers' attitudes, technological knowledge, and skills play significant roles in effective technology integration.

Despite the extensive literature on technology integration and student motivation, there is limited research on examining how teachers' computer efficacy influences their selection and frequency of motivational methods in online teaching and learning environments. This study fills this gap by providing empirical information regarding the correlation between college

instructors' computer efficacy and their utilisation of diverse incentive strategies across several categories.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research survey design to examine the differences in strategies used by college teachers to motivate students in online teaching-learning, in relation to their computer efficacy. College teachers' computer efficacy was the independent variable, and strategies for motivating students in online teaching-learning was the dependent variable.

Sample

The sample was drawn from college teachers representing various disciplines and levels of teaching experience, affiliated with Himachal Pradesh University. 140 college teachers were selected for the sample of the study. The sample was equally divided into high computer efficacy (N=70) and low computer efficacy (N=70) groups. The classification of high and low computer efficacy was based on teachers' self-reported scores on a standardised computer efficacy scale.

Tools Used

The research instrument was adapted from established measures of computer efficacy and online teaching practices. The tool consisted of two main sections:

- 1. Computer Efficacy Scale:** This scale was developed by the researcher and consists of 18 items with 5 choices for each statement, measuring teachers' confidence in using computers for various educational tasks, rated on a Likert scale. Based on total scores, teachers were categorized into high and low computer efficacy groups.
- 2. Strategies used by college teachers to motivate students in online teaching-learning:** This scale includes 20 items with 5 choices each, assessing the frequency of using specific strategies to motivate students in online teaching-learning. These are categorized into four areas: i.e., communication tools for introducing topics (Text-messages, audio messages, short-video messages); social media channels for encouraging students' engagement (WhatsApp groups, Facebook groups, Twitter chats); interactive digital tools for fostering interest (breakout rooms, interactive videos, animations, simulations, virtual study groups); and strategies for sharing success stories (inviting guest speakers, organizing online interviews with professionals/alumni, creating case studies based on real-life success stories, and organizing webinars featuring former students' success stories). Responses

were recorded on a five-point frequency scale: Never, Rarely, Sometimes, Often, and Always.

4. Data Collection and Analysis

Data were collected through both online and offline administration of these two scales. The t-test was used to examine, item by item, whether there is a significant difference in the use of strategies for motivating students in online teaching-learning by college teachers having high and low computer efficacy. Statistical significance was evaluated at the 0.05 and 0.01 levels.

Results and Analysis

Scores of college teachers on computer efficacy were arranged in descending order. The top 70 college teachers (approximately 25%) were categorized as the high computer efficacy group, whereas the bottom 70 college teachers (approximately 25%) formed the low computer efficacy group. The table below presents the mean, standard deviation, and t-values for college teachers having high and low computer efficacy with respect to their use of strategies for motivating students in the online teaching-learning process. The findings are summarized in Table 1.1 as follows:

Table 1.1: Difference in the use of Strategies for Motivating Students in Online Teaching-Learning by College Teachers having High and Low Computer Efficacy

Sr. No.	Items	Computer Efficacy Levels	N	Mean	SD	't'	Remarks
A.	I send introductory notes to students regarding the topic to be taught by using:						
1	Text-messages	High	70	3.20	1.28	2.40	Significant at the 0.05 level
		Low	70	2.69	1.24		
2	Audio messages	High	70	3.29	1.19	3.56	Significant at the 0.01 level
		Low	70	2.60	1.08		
3	Short video-message	High	70	3.20	1.23	1.53	NS

		Low	7 0	2.91	0.9 4		
B.	I encourage students to engage with each other and with the course material through social media channels such as						
4	WhatsApp Groups	High	7 0	4.40	0.8 0	2.0 4	Significant at the 0.05 level
		Low	7 0	4.09	1.0 0		
5	Facebook Groups	High	7 0	2.71	1.3 5	1.4 6	NS
		Low	7 0	2.39	1.3 0		
6	Twitter Chats	High	7 0	2.27	1.3 8	2.8 9	Significant at the 0.01 level
		Low	7 0	1.70	0.9 0		
C.	I facilitate students' interest in the subject matter by using:						
7	Breakout Rooms	High	7 0	2.87	1.2 9	0.9 3	NS
		Low	7 0	2.69	1.0 2		
8	Interactive videos	High	7 0	3.69	0.9 8	3.7 7	Significant at the 0.01 level
		Low	7 0	3.00	1.1 5		
9	Animations	High	7 0	3.19	1.2 1	3.7 8	Significant at the 0.01 level
		Low	7 0	2.43	1.1 4		
10	Simulations	High	7 0	3.10	1.2 1	3.5 5	

		Low	7 0	2.40	1.1 0		Significant at the 0.01 level
11	Virtual Study Groups	High	7 0	3.13	1.2 7	1.0 7	NS
		Low	7 0	2.90	1.2 4		
D.	I share success stories related to the subject matter by:						
12	Inviting Guest speakers	High	7 0	3.07	1.2 0	1.4 5	NS
		Low	7 0	3.33	0.8 4		
13	Organising online interview with professionals/ alumni	High	7 0	2.90	1.2 0	1.0 1	NS
		Low	7 0	2.70	1.1 3		
14	Conducting Case studies based on real-life success stories	High	7 0	3.20	1.0 8	0.6 2	NS
		Low	7 0	3.09	1.0 8		
15	Organising Webinars featuring former students' success stories	High	7 0	3.00	1.2 0	1.5 2	NS
		Low	7 0	2.70	1.1 2		

NS-Not Significant

Difference in the Use of Communication Tools for Introducing the Topic to be Taught

It is evident from Table 1.1 that, for motivating students in the online teaching-learning process, the obtained t-value of 2.40 with $df=138$, which is significant at the 0.05 level, indicates that college teachers with high computer efficacy ($M=3.20$) reported higher use of text messages than college teachers with low computer efficacy ($M=2.69$). Similarly, the obtained t-value of 3.56, $df=138$ (significant at the 0.01 level), indicates that college teachers with high computer efficacy ($M=3.29$) reported higher use of audio messages than college teachers with low computer efficacy ($M=2.60$). These results indicate that, to motivate students in online

teaching-learning, college teachers with high computer efficacy use text messages and audio messages significantly better than college teachers with low computer efficacy for sending introductory notes to students regarding the topic to be taught in online classes. Figures 1 and 2 show a significant difference between college teachers with high and low computer efficacy in the use of text messages and audio messages to send introductory notes to students regarding the topic to be taught in online classes.

However, no significant difference emerged between college teachers with high and low Computer Efficacy in the use of short-video messages ($t=1.53$), suggesting that college teachers with high and low computer efficacy use short-video messages in a similar manner to send introductory notes to students regarding the topic to be taught in online classes.

Figure 1: Difference in the use of text messages for sending introductory notes to motivate students in the online teaching-learning process by the college teachers having high and low Computer Efficacy.

Figure 2: Difference in the use of audio messages for sending introductory notes to motivate students in the online teaching-learning process by the college teachers having high and low Computer Efficacy.

Difference in the Use of Social Media Channels for Student Engagement

From Table 1.1, it may be observed that for motivating students in the online teaching-learning process, the obtained t-value of 2.04 with $df=138$, which is significant at the 0.05 level, indicates that college teachers with high computer efficacy ($M=4.40$) reported greater use of WhatsApp groups than college teachers with low computer efficacy ($M=4.09$). Similarly, the obtained t-value of 2.89, $df=138$ (significant at the 0.01 level), indicates that for motivating students in the online teaching-learning process, college teachers with high computer efficacy ($M=2.27$) reported higher use of Twitter chats than those with low computer efficacy ($M=1.70$). These results indicate that, to motivate students in the online teaching-learning process, college

teachers with high computer efficacy were more active in adopting social media platforms, such as WhatsApp groups and Twitter chats, to promote student motivation than their counterparts with low computer efficacy. Figures 3 and 4 show a significant difference between college teachers with high and low computer efficacy in the use of WhatsApp groups and Twitter chats to encourage students to engage with one another and the course material, as a strategy to motivate students in the online teaching-learning process.

However, no significant difference was observed between college teachers with high and low computer efficacy in their use of Facebook groups ($t=1.46$), suggesting that they use Facebook groups similarly to encourage students to engage with one another and the course material, as a strategy to motivate students in the online teaching-learning process.

Figure 3- Difference in the use of WhatsApp Groups for encouraging students to engage with each other and with the course material by the college teachers having high and low Computer Efficacy.

Figure 4: Difference in the use of Twitter Chats for encouraging students to engage with each other and with the course material by the college teachers having high and low Computer Efficacy.

Difference in the Use of Interactive Digital Tools to Facilitate Students’ Interest in the Subject Matter

It is evident from Table 1.1 that for motivating students in the online teaching-learning process, the obtained t-value of 3.77 with $df=138$, which is significant at the 0.01 level, indicates that college teachers with high computer efficacy ($M=3.69$) reported greater use of Interactive videos than college teachers with low computer efficacy ($M=3.00$). Similarly, the obtained t-value of 3.78 with $df=138$ (Significant at the 0.01 level) indicates that college teachers with high computer efficacy ($M=3.19$) reported higher use of animations than college teachers with low computer efficacy ($M=2.43$). Further, the t-value of 3.55 with $df=138$ (Significant at 0.01

level) reflects a highly significant difference between college teachers with high computer efficacy (M=3.10) and college teachers having low computer efficacy (M=2.40) in the use of simulations. These results show that, in motivating students in online teaching-learning, college teachers with high computer efficacy use Interactive videos, Animations, and Simulations significantly more than college teachers with low computer efficacy to foster students' interest in the subject matter. Figures 5, 6, and 7 reflect a significant difference between college teachers with high and low Computer Efficacy in the use of Interactive videos, animations, and simulations to facilitate students' interest in the subject matter and motivate them in online teaching-learning.

However, no significant difference was observed between college teachers with high and low computer efficacy in the use of breakout rooms ($t=0.93$) and virtual study groups ($t=1.07$) to facilitate students' interest in the subject matter, indicating that college teachers with high and low computer efficacy use breakout rooms and virtual study groups in a similar manner to facilitate students' interest in the subject matter.

Figure 5: Difference in the use of interactive videos for facilitating students' interest in the subject matter by the college teachers having high and low Computer Efficacy.

Figure 6: Difference in the use of animations for facilitating students' interest in the subject matter by the college teachers having high and low Computer Efficacy.

Figure 7: Difference in the use of simulations for facilitating students' interest in the subject matter by the college teachers having high and low Computer Efficacy.

Difference in the Strategies for Sharing Success Stories related to the Subject Matter for Students' Motivation

Table 1.1 reveals that for sharing success stories related to the subject matter college teachers having high and low computer efficacy use strategies i.e. inviting guest speakers ($t=1.45$), organising online interviews with professionals or alumni ($t=1.01$), Conducting Case studies based on real-life success stories ($t=0.62$) and organizing webinars featuring former students' success stories ($t=1.52$) almost in similar manner for students' motivation in online teaching-learning.

5. Discussion of the findings

The findings of the study revealed that significant differences between college teachers with high and low computer efficacy were evident only in the use of text-messages ($t=2.40$) and audio messages ($t=3.56$) for sending the introductory notes to students regarding the topic to be taught, WhatsApp Groups ($t=2.04$) and Twitter chats ($t=2.89$) for encouraging students to engage with each other and with the course material, Interactive videos ($t=3.77$), animations ($t=3.78$) and simulations ($t=3.55$) for facilitating students' interests in the subject matter, with college teachers having high computer efficacy employing these strategies more than college teachers having low computer efficacy to motivate students in online teaching-learning. Darius et al. (2021) identified animations, digital collaborations, and video lectures as effective methods for online learning. However, for the use of short video messages to send introductory notes to students regarding the topic to be taught, Facebook groups to encourage students with each other and with the course materials, breakout rooms and virtual study groups for facilitating students' interest in the subject matter, inviting guest speakers, organising online

interviews and webinars with professionals/alumni and conducting case studies based on real-life success stories to share success stories related to the subject matter, college teachers with high and low computer efficacy did not differ significantly, indicating that they used these strategies in a similar manner. This pattern aligned with Rogers' (1995) diffusion of innovations theory, which proposes that the adoption of innovations is influenced by perceived complexity. Teachers with high computer efficacy may be more willing to adopt complex innovations, while those with lower efficacy tend to prefer simpler, more familiar tools. The findings indicated that professional development programs for online teaching should be tailored according to teachers' levels of computer efficacy. For teachers with low efficacy, programs might focus on building foundational confidence with widely accessible tools such as short-video messages, Facebook and basic video conferencing features before introducing more advanced strategies. For those with moderate efficacy, targeted skill development for specific tools- like breakout rooms and virtual study groups -could enhance their motivational toolkit. For highly computer efficacious teachers, advanced workshops on emerging technologies such as virtual reality and artificial intelligence applications might help sustain engagement and foster innovation.

References

- Aithal, P. S. (2023). *Using information communication and computation technology (ICCT) for re-defining higher education in India—A roadmap*. In P. K. Misra & N. S. Sabharwal (Eds.), *India Higher Education Report 2024: Technology and Higher Education* (pp. 55-77). Routledge.
- Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). *Teaching-learning process in higher education institutions*. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education*, 2(1), 2196-2206.
- Akram, H., Abdelrady, A. H., Al-Adwan, A. S., & Ramzan, M. (2022). *Teachers' perceptions of technology integration in teaching-learning practices: A systematic review*. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1-10.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change*. *Psychological Review*, 84(2), 191-215.
- Darius, P. S. H., Gundabattini, E., & Solomon, D. G. (2021). *A survey on the effectiveness of online teaching-learning methods for university and college students*. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series B*, 102(6), 1321-1330.
- Keller, J. M. (1983). *Motivational design of instruction*. In C. Reigeluth (Ed.), *Instructional design theories and models* (pp. 383-434). Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Ministry of Human Resource Development. (2020). *National education policy 2020*. Government of India.
- Mishra, P. K., & Sabharwal, N. S. (Eds.). (2023). *India Higher Education Report 2024: Technology and Higher Education*. Routledge.
- Rogers, E. M. (1995). *Diffusion of innovations* (4th ed.). The Free Press.

- Sehar, S., & Alwi, S. K. K. (2023). *Correlation between teachers' digital competency and their self-efficacy in managing online classes. Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences, 11(2), 2196-2206.*
- Singh, R. N., & Hurley, D. C. (2017). *The effectiveness of teaching-learning process in online education as perceived by university faculty and instructional technology professionals. Journal of Teaching and Learning with Technology, 6(1), 65-75.*
- Surry, D. W., & Land, S. M. (2000). *Strategies for motivating higher education faculty to use technology. Innovations in Education and Training International, 37(2), 145-153.*
- Valentin, A., Mateos, P. M., Gonzalez-Tablas, M. M., Perez, L., Lopez, E., & Garcia, I. (2013). *Motivation and learning strategies in the use of ICTs among university students. Computers & Education, 61, 52-58.*
- Yang, F. (2023). *Strategies for motivating students in college English classroom teaching. Journal of Education and Educational Research, 5(3), 1-6.*